

INTERACTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING PRACTICAL EXERCISES IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article presents interactive methods for conducting practical classes in higher educational institutions. At the same time, all methods and directions for conducting practical and laboratory classes with students studying in higher educational institutions are shown.

Key words: method, teaching, student, classes, teacher

INTRODUCTION This article highlights interactive methods for conducting practical (laboratory) classes with students. These directions are important in the formation of in-depth knowledge and skills that allow students to find solutions to various scientific and technical issues that arise during practical classes in higher education. Because in the course of practical classes, the student acquires the ability to independently solve practical problems and defend his ideas and solutions to the team, using the theoretical knowledge gained and existing regulatory documents, reference books and modern

1. GENERAL RULES

The purpose of practical (seminar) classes is to create opportunities for in-depth study of theory, the acquisition of practical skills and the development of students' independent creative thinking. Responsibilities:

- reflection of modern achievements of science in the educational process;
 - deepening the theoretical and practical training of students;
 - approximation of the educational process to the real working conditions of a particular specialist;
 - application of the acquired knowledge in practice, the formation of accounting and calculation skills;
 - development of initiative and independence of students;
 - formation of public speaking skills, the ability to present research results, the ability to lead a discussion;
 - formation of general professional and professional competencies;
 - control the development of pedagogical science.
- Tasks of practical (seminar) classes:

- educational and cognitive - consolidation, expansion, deepening of knowledge gained in lectures and in the course of self-study;
 - educational - school of speech, development of skills - selection and generalization of information;
 - encouragement - a certain incentive to test your creative powers and prepare for more active work;
 - educational - the formation of a worldview and faith, independence, scientific research, competitiveness, education of courage;
 - control - checking the quality of knowledge and independent work of the student. Teaching students in practical and seminar sessions is aimed at:
 - generalization, systematization, deepening, consolidation of what has been obtained in science
- on the formation of skills for applying the acquired knowledge in practice (analytical, design, constructive, etc.);
- realizing the unity of intellectual and practical activity;
 - on the formation of practical skills for performing certain actions and operations necessary in further professional activities;
 - development of professionally important qualities, such as independence, responsibility, accuracy in solving problems.

There are various types of practical and seminar classes:

- control and educational seminar - a lesson with a frontal survey, written tests;
- training seminar - a lesson focused on independent performances of students;
- creative discussion, debates, public defense of abstracts; - practical lesson on problem solving, situation analysis, business games.

2. INTERACTIVE PRACTICE LEARNING METHODS

The interactive teaching methods presented in this collection include: memory exercise for students.

1. Problem-based learning technology Problem-based learning technology is a developmental learning technology that stimulates the process of active learning and forms a logical sequence of thinking. This technology is one of the most effective technologies in high school. The essence of problem-based learning lies in the teacher's management of the assimilation of new knowledge by organizing problem situations in teaching students and solving educational (best, life) tasks, problems and questions.

2. The "case study" method. "Case-study" - the English word ("case" - a specific situation, event, "stadi" - study, analyze) is considered a teaching method based on the study and analysis of specific situations. This method was first used at

Harvard University in 1921 with the aim of using practical situations in the study of economic management sciences.

3. Method "Hard attack of thoughts". The essence of the "Cruel Attack of Ideas" method is as follows: they help to realize the personal potential of each student performing certain tasks in a team; is to develop in students the ability to put forward an idea contrary to the opinion expressed by a certain community (group). This method can be successfully applied in the process of education organized in social sciences, humanities and natural sciences.

4. Discussion method of teaching Levers for managing a controversial practical exercise

The moderator assumes all tasks - managing the stages of discussion, confirming the validity and correctness of answers, determining the terms and concepts used, the correct use of relations, etc.

Properly manage the distribution of materials. The reviewer will have to determine the directions of the reports of the parties and evaluate them as a whole: relevance, scientific aspect, logic and clarity of questions, clarity of presentation of conclusions. Competitors form a competitive process between accepted studies. He can not only criticize the main position of the speaker, but also find weaknesses or errors in his ideas and offer his own decisive points.

Expert - evaluates the productivity of all discussions, including the opinions expressed by the participants in the discussion, conclusions drawn, suggestions and hypotheses.

5. Brainstorming method. The "brainstorming" method, first used in 1963 by OSBORNE (an American scientist), is universal. The task of "brainstorming" is to create new ideas with the help of a microgroup, or the strength of the microgroup as a whole is greater than the sum of the strengths of its individual members.

Brainstorming is enough to motivate problem solvers to come up with more ideas, including incredible and even fantastic ones, and create new ones. The more ideas, the more likely it is that at least one of them is the same term. This is the basic principle of the Mental Attack method. The use of the methods listed and above is considered the main factor in increasing the competence, knowledge and quality of education of each teacher and student. In addition, when using these factors in the implementation of methods, it is advisable to work with an understanding of their true nature and rules of procedure. Each method serves to further improve the quality of education in higher educational

institutions, to strengthen students' independent thinking, theoretical and practical knowledge.

CONCLUSION In the education system, the sequence of lectures and practical exercises is important. Pedagogical experience shows that practical learning cannot be limited to developing practical skills and solving problems, scheduling, etc. Students should always see the guiding idea of the course and its relevance to practice. The purpose of the lesson should be clear not only to the teacher, but also to the students. This gives relevance to educational work, confirms the need to master the experience of professional activity and connects it with life practice. Under such conditions, the teacher's task is to show students the practical significance of leading scientific ideas and fundamental scientific concepts and rules in practical and seminar classes.

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